

HISTOMORPHOLOGICAL STUDIES OF HARD TOOTH TISSUE IN CHILDREN WITH ENAMEL HYPOPLASIA BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE DENTAL DIAGNOSTIC SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Dentine defects are the result of developmental disorders and can significantly affect the health and functionality of teeth. Among such defects, dentinal dysplasia and imperfect dentinogenesis are distinguished. Dentine dysplasia is manifested by darkening of the tooth crown, increased tooth mobility and frequent abscesses that occur without the presence of caries. This condition is characterized by a pathological change in the structure of dentin, which leads to the above symptoms. Imperfect dentinogenesis is another serious disorder characterized by thinning of the coronal structure of the tooth..

Tooth fusion, or fusion, can occur between two teeth with a normal bite or between one normal tooth and an excess tooth. This phenomenon leads to a decrease in the number of teeth in the dental arch, which can affect occlusion and aesthetics [6]. Differences in tooth size can be caused by both genetic factors and changes in jaw size. Increasing the size of teeth, known as macrodontia, and decreasing the size, called microdontia, are important aspects of dental pathology. These abnormalities require an individual approach in diagnosis and treatment in order to restore normal dental function and aesthetics[5].

Dilaxation is a term for teeth that are characterized by bends or changes in the long axis of the crown, crown-root, or root. This disorder often occurs as a result of trauma to the developing dental bud, and the severity of dilaxation depends on the severity of the initial injury. Such teeth may not erupt properly, which requires an assessment of their viability and a decision on further treatment. A concretion is a pathological junction of two adjacent teeth on the surface of their roots. This type of anomaly can complicate endodontic and surgical treatment. Taurodontism is an anomaly in which the furcation zones on the molar teeth are located more apically, which leads to an elongated shape of the pulp chamber. This feature may complicate endodontic treatment and requires special attention during diagnosis [7,9].

Hutchinson's incisors and mulberry molars are specific defects observed on incisors and molars in patients who have suffered from congenital syphilis. These changes in the shape of teeth serve as a diagnostic sign of this disease [8]. Odontomas are tumors that are usually located in the alveolar process and prevent the eruption of adjacent or subsequent teeth. Since odontomas can significantly disrupt the normal development of the dentition, their surgical removal is necessary [10].

Defects in dentin are the result of abnormalities in its development and can significantly affect the health and functionality of teeth. Among such defects, dentinal dysplasia and imperfect dentinogenesis are distinguished. Dentine dysplasia is manifested by darkening of the tooth crown, increased tooth mobility and frequent abscesses that occur without the presence of caries. This condition is characterized by a pathological change in the structure of dentin, which leads to the above symptoms. Imperfect dentinogenesis is another serious disorder characterized by thinning of the coronal structure of the tooth [3].

Abnormal dentin development may result in pulp exposure, which increases the risk of infections and other complications. There are three types of dentinogenesis imperfecta: type I is associated with osteogenesis imperfecta, a systemic disease that affects bones and teeth; type II affects teeth exclusively, and type III is characterized by so-called "shell" teeth, which have an unusual structure and shape [30]. Another possible disorder is a dentinal cyst, which, although rarely symptomatic, can lead to the formation of dentinal lesions. These cysts require attention, as they can complicate treatment and affect the condition of surrounding tissues [4,8].

The cement covering the root of the tooth may also experience defects associated with a violation of its formation. The classification of such defects is based on the amount of cement formed: hypocementosis is characterized by an insufficient amount of cement, hypercementosis by excessive cement formation, and acementosis by the complete absence of a cement layer. These anomalies can affect the stability of teeth in the alveolar bone and require a special treatment approach. Hypercementosis is a pathological accumulation of cement around the roots of teeth, which is usually detected by X-ray examination. This condition may be associated with chronic inflammatory processes or systemic diseases such as Paget's disease. Hypercementosis, as a rule, does not cause symptoms, but in some cases it can lead to difficulties during endodontic treatment or tooth extraction [4,7].

Hypocementosis, on the contrary, is characterized by a thin layer of cement, which can contribute to the development of periodontal problems and an increased risk of tooth loss due to insufficient root fixation in the alveolar bone. This condition may be related to genetic factors, metabolic disorders, or age-related changes. Acementosis is a rare disease in which cement does not form at all. This is due to defects in the work of cement blasts, the cells responsible for the formation of cement. Acementosis leads to significant problems with dental stability and may require comprehensive treatment to preserve the dentition [4].

Defects involving all three major hard structures of the tooth (enamel, dentin, and cement) include regional odontodysplasia. This condition is characterized by damage to all three structures in one quadrant in humans and is accompanied by significant impairments in the formation of teeth. Imperfect odontogenesis, which also belongs to this group, is characterized by insufficient enamel formation, which is often associated with disorders in

the dentin structure. These pathologies can significantly complicate treatment and require a specialized approach [5]. Aplasia, or anodontia, is an extremely rare condition in which teeth do not develop at all.

This leads to the absence of dental ridges and a marked decrease in the vertical height of the face, which significantly affects the appearance and functionality of the dental system. Treatment of anodontia requires an integrated approach, including orthodontic and surgical correction methods [4,8]. Treatment of dental development disorders includes therapeutic methods to restore the structure of teeth, orthopedic and surgical interventions to correct the shape and bite, as well as genetic counseling for hereditary pathologies[7].

Prevention is aimed at preventing the effects of teratogenic factors during pregnancy, ensuring adequate intake of vitamins and minerals, regular dental monitoring and the use of fluorides to strengthen the enamel. An integrated approach to treatment and prevention makes it possible to effectively manage these disorders. Dental development disorders are a complex and multifactorial process, including genetic, epigenetic, and external influences that can disrupt the normal formation of teeth at different stages of embryogenesis. These pathologies manifest themselves in various clinical forms, from changes in the structure and shape of teeth to their complete absence [8,11].

Effective treatment requires a comprehensive approach that includes both therapeutic and orthopedic methods, as well as surgical intervention for more serious abnormalities. Prevention plays a key role in reducing the risk of these disorders and should be based on controlling the effects of adverse factors, ensuring adequate nutrition and regular dental monitoring. In the future, special attention should be paid to the development of genetic and molecular technologies that can open up new opportunities for early diagnosis and individualized treatment of these pathologies. Additional research in the field of epigenetic mechanisms and environmental influences on dental development may contribute to a deeper understanding of the pathogenesis of these disorders and the development of more effective preventive strategies [3,6].

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